

ELECTRICAL MONITORING OF FATIGUE IN CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

There is considerable existing literature covering a variety of approaches to utilising the conductive properties of carbon fibre to locate and characterise damage within composite parts. This paper examines electrical behaviour during dynamic loading in flexure, building on extant work which demonstrates the basic feasibility of electrically monitoring fatigue processes in carbon fibre reinforced composites.

Preliminary work on thin, monolithic specimens of woven carbon reinforced epoxy, indicates that the change in resistivity with loading is significantly time-dependent, and non-linear with respect to stress or strain. In this paper, initial data is presented which supports this and appears to agree with other recent work on similar materials in tension-tension fatigue. Clearly these phenomena need to be further characterised before electrical monitoring can be fully utilised for dynamic tests.

1 INTRODUCTION

Since very early in the development of fibre reinforced polymers, it has been observed that damage accumulation affects the resistivity of the material [1]. As the mechanical behaviour and underlying micromechanics came to be well understood, and carbon fibre reinforcement became commercially important for structural applications, various researchers analysed the relationship between damage and changing electrical characteristics [2-6]. The logical extrapolation of this was seeking to localise the damage within a test coupon [4,6,7] and ultimately to map areas of significant mechanical damage on larger test pieces and potentially components in service [8-11].

A majority of other work has been focused on long-term structural health monitoring, but clearly there is some potential for the use of electrical resistance in monitoring fatigue damage accumulation, the basic feasibility of which has been demonstrated in a number of materials and test modes [12-16]. Some researchers have observed clear correlation between the changing resistivity and mechanical measures of damage (eg. strain amplitude, specimen compliance, etc) [12,14,15], while others have examined a less direct, empirical relationship between resistivity data and ultimate fatigue life [16].

The aim of this work was to assess the potential to use the latest dynamic test control systems and software to extract more useful data from electrical monitoring, analysing the phase correlation between resistance and cyclically applied stress or strain. The author originally proposed that this could prove of particular interest on sandwich structures, which are difficult to instrument. However, preliminary work on thin, monolithic specimens of woven carbon epoxy revealed some phenomena which need to be characterised before electrical monitoring can be fully utilised for dynamic tests. This paper presents an analysis of the implications of data collected so far.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Specimens

For the purposes of initial investigation, specimens were cut from an existing sample of material; this was known to have been produced from a high temperature cured epoxy prepreg with plain weave carbon fibre reinforcement in a symmetric lay-up, with alternate 0°/90° ply sequence. The finished laminate thickness was typically 2mm.

Specimens were cut to a size of 120 mm x 10 mm using a water cooled diamond saw. The surface of the composite was cleaned and finely abraded, to allow 2 electrodes to be applied using silver paste adhesive. Electrodes 4 mm wide were applied at a separation of 20 mm (at the near edges), and connected as a simple potential divider (i.e. half-bridge) with a 100 k Ω resistor, using the internal 15V power supply of the controller.

2.2 Test Equipment Control and measurement

The load frame used was an Instron Electropuls E3000 electrodynamic test machine, with linear electric motor drive. WaveMatrix 1.8 test control software was used to set up and record the tests, and to perform live calculations. For these initial experiments, specimens were loaded in a simple three-point bending mode, with a support span of 80 mm, and the electrodes on the tensile face of the specimen, as shown in Figure 1. Thin pads (1 mm) of stiff nitrile rubber were used to electrically insulate the specimen from external potential and prevent a parallel circuit through the test fixture, as well as avoiding extraneous effects at contact points through surface wear or indentation.

Figure 1: Electropuls E3000 dynamic test system with bend fixture, and instrumented specimen

2.3 Electrical Measurement

Connection of the instrumented specimen was made to the Instron 8800MT test control and data acquisition system, as a low level direct current analogue input, with half-bridge fixed excitation (see also 2.1). The controller was configured to use a full scale input of 5 mV resulting in a nominal sensitivity of 0.3 μ V. Background noise level was established as \pm XX μ V with the specimen in the test fixture and the actuator powered, but not applying a load.

3 RESULTS

The basic connection of the specimen and tracking of electrical signal was first tested using a swept frequency from 0.2 Hz up to 10.2 Hz, in increments of 0.2 Hz. Since displacement (or position) is the most reliable mode of control on any dynamic system, this method was selected, applying a sinusoidally varying deflection to the specimen. Displacement set point was fixed as 0.1mm for this test, with all sine waveforms phased to start at 90° (i.e. cosine wave from minimum deflection). Different amplitudes were applied with the aim of correlating the change in voltage output (proportional to the change in resistance) to the load and deflection.

As can be seen in Figure 2, at small deflections, the signal appears to trace a reasonable sine wave at a range of frequencies. It is little surprise that at low amplitude, the signal-to-noise is fairly poor,

meaning that its impact could become significant at anything other than very slow cyclic loading. Although amplitude of variation appears to be comparable across the frequency range, unfortunately, there must already be some concern that the same specimen, during the same test, appears to be exhibiting a higher average resistance at higher test frequency, despite the fact that it must be subject to the same deflection and therefore strain levels.

Figure 2: Electrical response to 0.4 mm peak-to-peak sinusoid at varying frequency

The tracking starts to fail, or at least become non-linear, at larger amplitudes; in Figure 3 it can be seen that a secondary effect is superimposed on the rising and falling edges. The effect increases with increasing frequency. Furthermore the baseline (starting point) is now so strongly affected by frequency, that the unloaded signal at 9.8 Hz is almost as great as the fully loaded signal at 0.2 Hz.

Figure 3: Electrical response to 2.5 mm peak-to-peak sinusoid at varying frequency

At this point it seems unclear whether this is an effect of resonance, of strain rate, or some other factor. Figure 4 shows that, at 0.2 Hz, while applied force traces remain cleanly sinusoidal, the additional shoulders still appear with increasing displacement amplitude. Given the high stiffness of the specimen this effectively eliminates any likelihood that this is an anomaly caused by resonance.

Figure 4: Force and electrical response to varying sinusoidal displacement at 0.2 Hz

To eliminate any rate effects, tests were conducted at constant rate of loading, this time in force control to try to separate any influence due to the compliance of the rubber pads. A loading rate of 50 newtons per second was employed, loading and unloading twice to increasing peak level, with a 5 second hold after each ramp in both directions.

Based on data presented earlier, it is little surprise that the electrical signal does bear a superficial resemblance to the actuator displacement, but fails to track linearly to peak load. The rate of change in resistance is moderately repeatable for small changes in stress on both loading and unloading, meaning that the time and the gradient at the onset point of loading and both onset and offset points for unloading are clearly identifiable and well aligned with extrinsic measurements. The stable signal after unloading is gradually increasing, with increasing peak load, as is the displacement. Some limit of resistive proportionality appears to be reached at around 1mm deflection, but examining the unloading section, this is not a yield-like phenomenon, but rather a reversible non-linear relationship.

When considering the performance of the specimen as a transducer, it is of much greater concern that the peak signal exhibits quite significant relaxation while at constant load. In particular, although the mechanical displacement increases slightly, during this relaxation at constant load, the electrical signal (which formerly increased with displacement) now decreases, indicating that a different phenomenon must be dominating.

Figure 5: Comparison of electrical and displacement response to trapezoid force control loading.

Given the apparent success of other researchers [11-15], it was decided to evaluate the behaviour of a specimen during a relatively short period of fatigue loading. A waveform of 4 mm peak deflection at a ratio of $R = 0.1$, was applied at a frequency of 3 Hz. In this test, there did seem to be some degree of correlation between electrical measurements and mechanical performance, as shown in Figure 6.

The maximum resistance certainly bears a basic similarity in profile with the maximum load (inverted) and the mechanical loss angle. It is unclear what caused the sudden drop in peak force at around 4700 cycles, but obviously this is not reflected by the specimen resistance signal. It will be noted that all cyclic trends become quite noisy after 6000 cycles, but there was no obvious physical cause for this, other than that the insulating pads were noted to have moved slightly when the test was stopped.

Figure 6: Comparison of electrical signal with mechanically derived measurements during fatigue.

In light of earlier observations concerning the unpredictable behaviour in the middle of the cycle, the data was also re-analysed to extract the rate of change of force and rate of change of resistance, on the rising edge of the loading cycle between 10% and 15% of the cycle time. This data is plotted in Figure 7; some, but not all gross features map between these measurements and there is no overall trend.

Figure 7: Evolution of force-rate and resistance-rate during displacement controlled fatigue.

4 DISCUSSION

At the time of writing, this project has only confirmed that some limited degree of correlation can be made between electrical resistivity of a carbon fibre reinforced composite and the accumulation of damage under fatigue loading. Careful examination of waveforms reveals some concerning behaviour, which prevented the intended application of phase correlation amongst other techniques. However, the presence of what appears to be hysteretic behaviour of resistivity during a loading cycle may yet prove useful in itself.

It does appear that the behaviour is sufficiently close to linear at small strains that the raw waveform could be useable for tests at small fractions of failure stress. However, in practical tests conducted so far and in literature where fatigue loading waveforms are published [12,13,14,16], the resistance (or voltage) data exhibited some clipping or anomalous shape of the peaks and troughs on the electrical signal, which appear similar those waveforms recorded during the present work. Since many fatigue tests are conducted at fairly high proportions of failure stress, in order to construct an S-N curve, this would tend to prohibit the application of this monitoring technique outside of very high cycle fatigue.

Using the signal in the simple ways used in this paper and other published work on fatigue, any form of correlation during a fatigue test is tied to a particular peak strain rate, since both the unloaded resistance and the resistance amplitude seem to vary with rate of deformation. Since some materials decrease in modulus significantly during the course of a fatigue test, this could prove problematic for a conventional high cycle fatigue test, conducted in load control at constant frequency. It would seem more compatible with constant strain-rate fatigue, such as proposed by Sims in the early 1980s.

The original aim of this work had been to use waveform correlation to extract more data from the varying resistance, but this must rely on a direct and consistent relationship between the electrical resistance and both the loading state and the damage accumulation in the material. Further work is ongoing to understand of these effects better; it is hoped that the application of a hysteresis model along the lines of that proposed by Abry et al [5] would enable the extraction of richer and more informative data during cyclic loading.

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